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Some Endemic Plant Taxa Growing in Çüngüş District of Diyarbakır Province of Turkey

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Abstract: This research was conducted in 2021 and 2022 in four different sections of the Savucak Mountain pasture in the Çüngüş district of Diyarbakır province. It was determined that the majority of the 12 endemic taxa belonging to 7 families, all of which are considered invasive taxa in terms of pasture, belonged to the Astraceae family, followed by plant taxa from the Boraginaceae, Araceae, Brassicaceae, Lamiaceae, Liliaceae, and Plantaginaceae families, respectively. The botanical composition of endemic plant taxa such as *Gundelia cappadocica*, *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri*, *Linaria genistifolia* subsp. *praealta*, *Phlomis linearis*, *Tanacetum cadmeum* subsp. *orientale*, *Tanacetum densum* subsp. *cadmeum*, and *Tulipa sintenisii*, identified in the study, was determined to vary between 0.16% and 15.26% in the northern, southern, eastern, and western sections of the pasture. The endemic taxa identified in this study have been noted in numerous researches as important species due to their use in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and dye industries. Therefore, it is considered essential to preserve these plant taxa both in their natural habitats (in situ) and outside their natural habitats (in gene banks) to ensure their survival.

1. Introduction

Meadow and pasture areas are the cheapest and most natural roughage production areas for animal husbandry (Açıkgöz et al., 2005). These areas are not only feeding areas for domestic animals, but also feeding and sheltering areas for flora and fauna (Çaçan and Yüksel, 2016). However, throughout our country, these areas have significantly lost their productivity and quality as a result of excessive and untimely grazing without complying with the grazing rules for many years (Gökkuş et al., 2009). This is supported by reports from some studies conducted in the Southeastern Anatolia Region, particularly in Diyarbakır and Mardin, which have shown that pasture vegetation is weak and invasive plants are dominant in these areas (Seydoşoğlu et al., 2015; Seydoşoğlu et al., 2019; Seydoşoğlu and Kökten, 2019). The climate change, the effects of which seen at the present, accelerates this process. For all these reasons, valuable and rarely encountered endemic forage plant species in meadows and pasture areas are also affected negatively (Hatipoğlu et al., 2019). It is important to research, identify and protect endemic taxa in meadows, pastures and natural vegetation before they become extinct (Karagöz et al., 2010). If we examine the endemic plants identified in the study in terms of their benefits to humanity: *Gundelia* taxa are generally used in chewing gum and food production by the public. The fresh stems of the plant collected in spring are cleaned and used after various processes. It is generally known for its roasting with eggs, rice, pickle and gum productions (Armağan et al., 2023). *Helichrysum* species, it has been used for centuries due to its biliary fluid enhancer (in addition to its kidney stone-reducing, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antimicrobial properties) in traditional medicine in the world (İnsel, 2019). It has been determined that *Linaria genistifolia* extract has antibiotic effects against some bacteria (Günter et al., 2020). *Phlomis* taxa are used by the public in Turkey as an appetite stimulant, antiallergic, central expectorant, antidiarrheal, carminative, stomach upset, painkiller, antidiabetic herbal tea and tonic (Akyol et al., 2010). In the Mediterranean Region, *Tanacetum cadmeum* subsp. *cadmeum* is used for ulcer, abdominal storage and cold maintenance by chewing (Tuzlacı and Erol, 1999), and its extract is seen to be the most effective pesticide among taxa belonging to the *Tanacetum* species (Susurluk et al., 2007). *Arum rupicola* is used in folk medicine for the treatment of diabetes in Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia. (Özok and Güneş, 2019). Extracts obtained from the *Achillea* plant have been found to have antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. (Çolak et al., 2020). *Alkanna* species are also used in the pharmaceutical industry, cosmetics and for dyeing liqueurs (Kayabaşı et al., 2000). *Paracaryum cristatum* subsp. *cristatum* is one of the endemic species with the most potential for use in landscape designs (Bozkurt, 2024). The dye content of the *Isatis aucheri* plant is quite high. For this reason, it can be used in dye production (Kızıllı, 2006). Thus, this study was carried out to determine the botanical composition of endemic taxa in vegetation, pasture quality grades and pasture conditions in different aspects of Savucak Mountain pastures in Çüngüş district of Diyarbakır province located in the Southeastern Anatolia Region of Turkey.

2. Material and Methods

The study was carried out in different sections (eastern, western, southern and northern sections) of Savucak Mountain in Çüngüş district of Diyarbakır province, between April 15-June 15, 2021 and April 15-June 15, 2022. In the research, the point quadrat method was used to measure the vegetation. During the two-year study, a total of 8 tape measure lines of 50 meters were drawn in each section; a total of 3200 observations were taken at 10 stops on each tape measure and 10 observations at each stop. In these observations, the ratio of each plant taxon was determined in the botanical composition. However, only endemic taxa were analyzed of all taxa identified in this study. According to the climate data obtained from Diyarbakır 15th General Directorate of Meteorology, the long-term average temperature of Çüngüş district is 15.7°C, January is the coldest month and August is the hottest month among the long-term averages.

The average annual temperature was 16.3°C, January was the coldest month and July was the hottest month in 2021, the average annual temperature was 15.4°C, January was the coldest month and August was the hottest month in 2022. When comparing rainfall amounts for the same months in different years, it is seen that the monthly amounts for long years are higher than all months except January and August of 2021; It is seen that the amount of rainfall in February, March, May, June, November and December of 2022 is higher than in all other months (Table 1).

Table 1. Some climate data of Çüngüş district (Anonymous, 2022)

Months	Temperature Average (°C)			Total Rainfall (mm)			Relative Humidity (%)		
	2021	2022	Long Years	2021	2022	Long Years	2021	2022	Long Years
January	3.3	0.6	2.2	216.4	151.6	181.91	62.2	64.3	72.0
February	5.9	4.9	4.7	19.9	88.1	84.90	53.6	61.7	65.5
March	7.1	4.0	8.6	112.9	184.8	130.0	54.0	61.1	62.5
April	14.9	15.6	13.1	2.4	8.8	70.49	43.5	38.9	54.8
May	22.0	17.1	18.9	7.9	80.7	45.59	28.0	44.8	47.1
June	25.4	25.1	24.8	0.1	16.6	14.79	26.4	33.8	31.7
July	30.3	29.4	29.5	0.5	0.3	1.23	23.5	24.1	22.6
August	29.7	30.6	29.7	3.8	1.2	2.61	25.0	24.2	22.1
September	23.8	25.6	24.8	0.6	0.0	9.18	28.0	24.5	26.2
October	17.5	18.5	17.6	53.4	8.2	60.21	32.8	36.8	42.3
November	11.6	10.6	9.8	39.9	233.4	68.15	54.8	62.4	54.1
December	4.0	3.2	4.7	105.8	271.2	195.23	61.1	67.2	70.7
Average/Total	16.3	15.4	15.7	563.6	1044.9	864.2	41.1	45.3	47.6

Soil samples taken from 0-30 cm depth from the pasture sections examined in the study were analyzed at Bingöl University, Faculty of Agriculture, Soil-Plant Analysis Laboratory (Table 2). It was determined that the soil structures of the examined sections were clayey-loamy in all sections, pH slightly acidic in the northern and western section, pH neutral in the southern and eastern sections, salt-free in all sections, rich in organic matter, very little lime, high in potassium and phosphorus levels; it was seen that the soil structures were similar in all four sections and there were no significant differences.

Table 2. Some soil analysis results of the study area

Analysis	Northern		Southern		Eastern		Western	
	Result	Explanation	Result	Explanation	Result	Explanation	Result	Explanation
Saturation (%)	60.23	Clay loam	55.1	Clay loam	52.25	Clay loam	63.8	Clay loam
pH	5.90	Low acidity	6.41	Neutral	6.71	Neutral	6.10	Low acidity
Salinity (%)	0.0064	No Salt	0.0072	No Salt	0.0074	No Salt	0.0083	No Salt
Organic Matter (%)	5.08	Rich	4.45	Rich	3.56	Rich	3.63	Rich
Lime (CaCO ₃) (%)	0.76	Very little	0.52	Very little	0.61	Very little	0.64	Very little
Potassium (K ₂ O) (kg/da)	59.52	High	46.74	High	51.35	High	55.34	High
Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅) (kg/da)	16.62	High	12.36	High	43.57	High	5.06	High

3. Results and Discussion

In the study, a total of 12 taxa belonging to 7 families were found and all of these taxa are perennial and belong to the invasive group. The highest number of taxa was found in *Astraceae* family (*Gundelia cappadocica*, *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri*, *Tanacetum cadmeum* subsp. *orientale*, *Tanacetum densum* subsp. *cadmeum*, *Achillea pseudoaleppica*), followed by *Boraginaceae* (*Alkanna megacarpa*, *Paracaryum cristatum* subsp. *cristatum*), *Araceae* (*Arum rupicola* var. *rupicola*), *Brassicaceae* (*Isatis aucheri*), *Lamiaceae* (*Phlomis linearis*), *Liliaceae* (*Tulipa sintenisii*) and *Plantaginaceae* (*Linaria genistifolia* subsp. *praealta*) families.

While 7 of the taxa (*Gundelia cappadocica*, *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri*, *Tanacetum cadmeum* subsp. *orientale*, *Tanacetum densum* subsp. *cadmeum*, *Phlomis linearis*, *Tulipa sintenisii*, *Linaria genistifolia* subsp. *praealta*) were identified by the point quadrat method, 5 (*Arum rupicola* var. *rupicola*, *Achillea pseudoaleppica*, *Alkanna megacarpa*, *Paracaryum cristatum* subsp. *cristatum*, *Isatis aucheri*) could not be sampled by the point quadrat tool in all pasture sections and were seen by chance in the study area. When the endemic taxa were examined according to pasture

sections, 4 of them were detected only in the southern section, 3 of them only in the eastern section, 2 in the eastern and southern sections, 1 in the eastern and western sections, and 2 in all sections of the pasture. Among the endemic taxa detected by the point quadrat method, *Tanacetum densum* subsp. *cadmeum* and *Linaria genistifolia* subsp. *praealta* are found only in the eastern section, *Tulipa sintenisii* is found only in the southern section, *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri* and *Phlomis linearis* were found in all sections of the pasture (Table 3).

Table 3. The family, group to which they belong, lifespan and sections where they were detected of the endemic taxa included in the study

Detected by the Point Quadrat Method				
Species	Family Name	Group	Life Span	Sections
<i>Gundelia cappadocica</i>	<i>Astraceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	S, E
<i>Helichrysum arenarium</i> subsp. <i>aucheri</i>	<i>Astraceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	N, S, E, W
<i>Tanacetum cadmeum</i> subsp. <i>orientale</i>	<i>Astraceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	E, W
<i>Tanacetum densum</i> subsp. <i>cadmeum</i>	<i>Astraceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	E
<i>Phlomis linearis</i>	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	N, S, E, W
<i>Tulipa sintenisii</i>	<i>Liliaceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	S
<i>Linaria genistifolia</i> subsp. <i>praealta</i>	<i>Plantaginaceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	E
Detected outside the Point Quadrat Method				
Species	Family Name	Group	Life Span	Sections
<i>Arum rupicola</i> var. <i>rupicola</i>	<i>Araceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	E
<i>Achillea pseudoaleppica</i>	<i>Astraceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	S, E
<i>Alkanna megacarpa</i>	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	S
<i>Paracaryum cristatum</i> subsp. <i>cristatum</i>	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	S
<i>Isatis aucheri</i>	<i>Brassicaceae</i>	Invasive	Perennial	S

*E: Eastern, S: Southern, N: Northern, W: Western

In the terms of botanical composition values of the endemic taxa, *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri* (1.59%) and *Phlomis linearis* (0.40%) were the most common plant taxa in the northern section, while other plant taxa were not encountered in this section. *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri* (8.81%), *Gundelia cappadocica* (0.96%), *Tulipa sintenisii* (0.96%) and *Phlomis linearis* (0.64%) were found in the southern section of pasture from highest to lowest values respectively, while no other endemic plant taxa were found in this section. All endemic plant taxa except *Tulipa sintenisii* were found in the eastern section and their botanical compositions were calculated as *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri* (15.26%), *Tanacetum cadmeum* subsp. *orientale* (4.05%), *Tanacetum densum* subsp. *cadmeum* (2.34%), *Phlomis linearis* (0.62%), *Gundelia cappadocica* (0.16%) and *Linaria genistifolia* subsp. *praealta* (0.16%). In the western section, *Helichrysum arenarium* subsp. *aucheri* (2.46%), *Phlomis linearis* (1.91%) and *Tanacetum cadmeum* subsp. *orientale* (0.55%) respectively, from highest to lowest (Table 4).

Table 4. Botanical compositions (%) of endemic taxa of pasture areas examined with point quadrat

Botanical Compositions (%)				
Taxa	Northern	Southern	Eastern	Western
<i>Gundelia cappadocica</i>	-	0.96	0.16	-
<i>Helichrysum arenarium</i> subsp. <i>aucheri</i>	1.59	8.81	15.26	2.46
<i>Linaria genistifolia</i> subsp. <i>praealta</i>	-	-	0.16	-
<i>Phlomis linearis</i>	0.40	0.64	0.62	1.91
<i>Tanacetum cadmeum</i> subsp. <i>orientale</i>	-	-	4.05	0.55
<i>Tanacetum densum</i> subsp. <i>cadmeum</i>	-	-	2.34	-
<i>Tulipa sintenisii</i>	-	0.96	-	-

The highest similarity index value of the endemic taxa among the pasture sections was found between the northern and western sections with 59.12%. This was followed by: southern and eastern

sections with 56.79%, southern and western sections with 39.80%, northern and southern sections with 32.87%, eastern and western sections with 26.16% respectively. The lowest value in terms of similarity index was determined between northern and eastern sections with 21.04%. These data show that the endemic taxa in the northern and western sections are close to each other in terms of soil coverage rates (Table 5).

Table 5. Similarity indices of endemic taxa belonging to the examined rangelands (%)

Similarity Indices (%)			
Sections	Northern	Southern	Eastern
Northern	32.87	59.12	21.04
Eastern	56.79	26.16	-
Western	39.80	-	-

In terms of pasture forage quality values, the highest value of these endemic taxa was found in the western section with 1.94, followed by the eastern section with 0.30, southern section with 0.12 and northern section with 0.02. Despite all these values, it was observed that the pasture quality grades of endemic taxa were "very poor" in all sections in terms of forage crops (Table 6).

Table 6. Pasture Quality Values of Examined Pasture Sections of Endemic Taxa

Pasture Quality Values				
Taxa	Northern	Southern	Eastern	Western
<i>Gundelia cappadocica</i>	-	0.00	0.00	-
<i>Helichrysum arenarium</i> subsp. <i>aucheri</i>	0.02	0.09	0.15	0.02
<i>Linaria genistifolia</i> subsp. <i>praealta</i>	-	-	0.01	-
<i>Phlomis linearis</i>	0.00	0.01	0.01	1.91
<i>Tanacetum cadmeum</i> subsp. <i>orientale</i>	-	-	0.08	0.01
<i>Tanacetum densum</i> subsp. <i>cadmeum</i>	-	-	0.05	-
<i>Tulipa sintenisii</i>	-	0.02	-	-
Total	0.02	0.12	0.30	1.94

As a result of the research, it has been concluded that it is very important that endemic taxa should be protected both in situ and in gene banks (ex-situ) in order to continue their generation that can contribute to pasture animal husbandry.

4. Conclusion

In this study, the endemic taxa detected in different areas of the pasture were generally in the invasive group with low feed quality values. Despite this, it is important to protect these taxa in the pasture in terms of both biodiversity and the continuity of the species.

Conflict of Interest

The Authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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